

BENZOYL CHLORIDE AS A POLAR SOLVENT. PART V. CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS IN BENZOYL CHLORIDE

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Acid base neutralisation reactions between the solvo-acids, like titanium tetrachloride, stannic chloride, zirconium tetrachloride, tellurium tetrachloride and antimony pentachloride, on the one hand, and the solvo-bases, like pyridine, quinoline, α -, β - and γ -picolines and dimethylaniline, on the other, have been carried out in benzoyl chloride, and the course of reactions has been followed conductometrically. The composition of the neutralisation complexes, as isolated and reported earlier (part III), has been confirmed and the existence of quite a few more has been indicated. The conductance of the solutions of solvo-acids and solvo-bases as well as their neutralisation has been explained on the basis of the ionisation of benzoyl chloride as : $BzCl \rightleftharpoons Bz^+ + Cl^-$.

Conductometric titrations have gained considerable importance in the study of acid-base neutralisation reactions in polar solvents (Smith, *Chem. Rev.*, 1938, 23, 165; Gutmann, *Monatsh.*, 1954, 85, 404; *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1951, 266, 331; Spandau and Brunneck, *ibid.*, 1955, 278, 197). Neutralisation reactions between acids and bases, characteristic of the solvo-system benzoyl chloride, have already been described in a previous paper (Paul, Chander and Singh, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 869). These reactions have now been studied conductometrically, and the existence of the complexes has been confirmed.

The specific conductances of the solutions of the solvo-bases, such as, α -, β - and γ -picolines and dimethylaniline, and the ansolvo-base, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride, in benzoyl chloride have been determined at 28°. The results (Table I) reveal that these solutions are more conducting than the solvent itself (specific conductance = 9×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 20°; Gutmann and Tennenberger, *Monatsh.*, 1957, 88, 216).

TABLE I

Specific conductance of benzoyl chloride = 9×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 20°.

Base.	Concentration (moles/litre).	Sp. conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹).
α -Picoline	0.0103	2.583×10^{-5}
β -Picoline	0.0100	2.253×10^{-5}
γ -Picoline	0.0100	2.280×10^{-5}
Dimethylaniline	0.0100	4.808×10^{-5}
Dimethylphenylbenzyl- ammonium chloride	0.0016	3.384×10^{-5}

This indicates that on dissolution of these substances in benzoyl chloride, ion pairs are formed which conduct electric current. Therefore, on the basis of the ionisation of benzoyl chloride as:

and the strongly electron-donor nature of the nitrogen in the tertiary bases, the structure of these solvo-bases in benzoyl chloride solutions can be represented as:

Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride is soluble in benzoyl chloride and in solution it must exist as ions:

Similar observations have been recorded (Gutmann and Tannenberger, *loc.cit.*) in the case of the Lewis acids, such as, stannic chloride, titanium tetrachloride, zirconium tetrachloride and antimony pentachloride. Solutions of these in benzoyl chloride are more conducting than the solvent itself, although some of them, such as, stannic chloride ("International Critical Tables", McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., N.Y. London, 1926, VI, p. 142) and titanium tetrachloride (Eingorn, *Ukrain Khim. Zhur.*, 1950, 16, 404), are non-conducting in the pure state. The mode of ionisation of the solutions of these acids and bases in benzoyl chloride has already been proposed (Paul, Chander and Singh, *loc.cit.*). Some conductometric titrations between tetraethylammonium chloride and a few solvo-acids in benzoyl chloride as solvent were carried out by Gutmann and Tannenberger (*Monatsh.*, 1957, 88, 292). In the present work the neutralisation reactions between the tetrachlorides of tin, titanium, zirconium and tellurium and the pentachloride of antimony as solvo-acids and pyridine, quinoline, α -, β - and γ -picolines and dimethylaniline as solvo-bases have been studied conductometrically. The formation of a number of compounds with different stoichiometric ratios (Paul, Chander and Singh, *loc.cit.*) has been confirmed and the formation of some new compounds has been indicated.

On the addition of a solution of stannic chloride in benzoyl chloride to a solution of α -picoline in the same solvent, a light yellow solid begins to separate, and the conductance of the solution falls progressively till at the point, where the acid/base molar ratio becomes 0.5 (Fig. 1), the conductance is at a minimum and the precipitation is complete. If the addition of the acid solution is continued beyond this point, the precipitate begins to dissolve slowly and the conductance increases rapidly till the second break occurs at the acid/base molar ratio of 1.0. Here the precipitate dissolves completely and the solution becomes clear. On further addition of the acid solution, the rate of increase of the conductance is not appreciable, and no further break in the curve is noticed.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

During this titration the conductance of the solution records enormous changes. This may be attributed to the addition and removal of ionic species from the reaction medium. The appearance of the precipitate in the beginning of the titration can be ascribed to the formation of bis-benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorostannate, according to the following reactions :

The progressive removal of the benzoyl- α -picolinium and the chloride ions from the solution to yield an insoluble precipitate on the addition of stannic chloride solution explains the decrease in the conductance, which reaches a minimum when the precipitation is complete. The rapid rise in conductance as a consequence of the dissolution of the precipitate can be attributed to the formation and subsequent ionisation of the soluble and highly ionised acid salt, benzoyl- α -picolinium benzoylhexachlorostannate,

Thus, the addition of stannic chloride solution increases the number of ions entering the reaction medium, and as a result, the conductance increases considerably. At the second break the dissolution of the precipitate or the conversion of the normal salt to the acid salt is complete, and any further addition to the acid solution has little effect on the conductance, as the solvo-acid, Bz_2SnCl_6 , is comparatively feebly ionised.

The conductance curves, obtained by titrating stannic chloride against β -picoline and γ -picoline, are also presented in Fig. 1. In both these cases, two breaks corresponding to acid/base molar ratio of 0.5 and 1.0 are obtained. These breaks may be attributed to the formation of the normal salts, which are insoluble, and the acid salts, which are soluble, in benzoyl chloride. The course of reaction in both these cases can be explained on lines similar to those given for titration with α -picoline.

Pyridine and quinoline have been used as solvo-bases for conductometric titrations in selenyl chloride (Smith, *loc.cit.*), phosphoryl chloride (Gutmann, *Monatsh.*, 1954, 85, 1077) and thionyl chloride (Spandau and Brunneck, *loc.cit.*). The former forms a monosolvate (Adkins and Thompson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2242) while the latter, a disolvate (Paul, Bains and Singh, *this Journal*, 1958, 35, 489) with benzoyl chloride. The addition of a solution of stannic chloride in benzoyl chloride to a solution of pyridine in benzoyl chloride lowers the conductance of the latter with the immediate separation of a white precipitate (Fig. 2). The continued addition of the stannic chloride solution results in a progressive fall in the conductance which reaches a minimum when the acid/base molar ratio is 0.5. With any further addition of the acid solution, the conductance increases rapidly. At a later stage, however, the rate of increase of conductance falls, but the precipitate does not dissolve completely even when

three times the volume of the acid solution, used at the point of minimum conductance, has been added.

The separation of the precipitate and the decrease in conductance at the beginning of the titration may be considered as due to the formation of the normal salt, *bis*-benzoylpyridinium hexachlorostannate. The reaction can be represented as:

The rise in conductance may be attributed to the formation and ionisation of the acid salt, benzoylpyridinium benzoylhexachlorostannate in solution as:

The difficulty in locating the second break, corresponding to the formation of the acid salt, may be regarded as due to the sparingly soluble character of the acid salt and the slow formation of the acid salt from the normal salt. The observations recorded in the titration of stannic chloride against quinoline (Fig. 2) are quite similar to those

FIG. 3
Dimethylaniline (0.7146M/l) against stannic chloride
(0.0926 g.).

obtained in the titration of pyridine, mentioned above, and can be explained in a similar way. In this case also, only one break corresponding to the formation of the normal salt, *bis*-benzoylquinolinium hexachlorostannate, is observed, although both the normal and the acid salts have been isolated and analysed in partially desolvated forms (Paul, Chander and Singh, *loc.cit.*).

Dimethylaniline is freely miscible with benzoyl chloride, and therefore has been used as a titrant in its titrations with the solvo-acids. On the addition of the solution of dimethylaniline in benzoyl chloride to that of stannic chloride, a sharp increase in the conductance of the latter solution is recorded (Fig. 3). The conductance

reaches its maximum when the base/acid molar ratio is 1.0, and thereafter it begins to decrease rapidly with the simultaneous separation of a white crystalline precipitate. At the base/acid molar ratio of 2.0, the conductance attains its minimum value. If the addition of the base solution is continued further, the conductance again begins to rise. The third break occurs when the base/acid molar ratio is 3.0. Any further addition of dimethylaniline solution increases the conductance only slightly. The explanation for the change in conductance during the titration can be offered on the basis of the existence of ion pairs in solution. The addition of dimethylaniline solution to that of stannic chloride results in the formation of the acid salt, which is soluble in benzoyl chloride and is highly ionised. The conductance of the solution therefore rises rapidly.

Just after the first break, the formation of the normal salt begins. This is insoluble and precipitates out. Due to the removal of the ions from the solution, the conductance begins to fall.

At the point of minimum conductance, the precipitation of the normal salt is complete. With further addition of the base, the formation of only slightly dissociated complex with the base/acid molar ratio of 3.0 starts and the conductance begins to increase. This is complete at the third break and thereafter the slow increase in conductance is due to addition of dimethylaniline solution only.

Titanium tetrachloride is soluble in benzoyl chloride only to a small extent and affords a monosolvate (Cullinane *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4106), which ionises as:

α -Picoline, on the other hand, is appreciably soluble in benzoyl chloride and solutions of fairly high concentration can be prepared. In the titration that follows, therefore, α -picoline has been used as a titrant.

On the addition of a solution of α -picoline in benzoyl chloride to that of titanium tetrachloride, the conductance increases progressively (Fig. 4). It reaches a maximum as the base/acid molar ratio becomes 1.0 and then begins to fall rapidly as a consequence of the separation of a yellow precipitate. The precipitation is complete at the base/acid molar ratio of 2.0 and the conductance is at its minimum. If the addition of α -picoline solution is continued, the conductance again begins to rise. The curve shows two breaks corresponding to the formation of the acid salt, benzoyl- α -picolinium benzoylhexachlorotitanate, and the normal salt, bis-benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorotitanate. The former, being highly ionised, is responsible for the rapid increase in the conductance in the beginning of the titration. However, due to the limited

solubility of the salt, it begins to go out of the solution phase as a yellow precipitate near the first break. Some points recorded near the first break therefore do not fall

FIG. 4
α-Picoline (0.3684 M/l) against TiCl_4 (0.1062 g.).

on the regular curve. The rapid decrease in the conductance after the first break is due to the removal of the ions from the solution on account of the formation of the insoluble normal salt. After the second break, the slow rise in conductance is due to the addition of the weakly ionised benzoyl- α -picolinium chloride solution. The formation of the acid salt and its subsequent ionisation may be represented as :

The formation of the normal salt can be represented as:

The tetrachlorides of tellurium and zirconium, like those of tin and titanium, behave as dibasic acids in benzoyl chloride. These do not form any solid solvates under ordinary

experimental conditions with benzoyl chloride (Paul, Baius and Singh, *loc.cit.*), but the existence of their solvates in solution is indicated by the high conductance of their solution. On account of the limited solubility of these tetrachlorides, the bases have been used as titrants.

The curves obtained for the titrations of α -picoline against tellurium tetrachloride (Fig. 5) and zirconium tetrachloride (Fig. 6) are quite similar to that obtained in the case of the titration of α -picoline against titanium tetrachloride. The curve in each case shows two breaks corresponding to the formation of the acid salt at the base/acid molar ratio of 1.0 and the normal salt at the base/acid molar ratio of 2.0. The acid salts, benzoyl- α -picolinium benzoylhexachlorotellurite and benzoyl- α -picolinium benzoylhexachlorozirconate, are soluble and ionised, while the normal salts, bis-benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorotellurite and bis-benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorozirconate, are insoluble and separate out as white solids. The explanation advanced in the case of the neutralisation of α -picoline with titanium tetrachloride is applicable in these cases also.

The observations recorded in the titrations of dimethylaniline against tellurium tetrachloride (Fig. 5) and zirconium tetrachloride (Fig. 6) are similar to those obtained in the titration of this base against stannic chloride. In both the cases three breaks corresponding to the base/acid molar ratios of 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 are noticed in the conduc-

tance curves. The course of reaction is similar to that of the neutralisation of stannic chloride against dimethylaniline, and can be explained on similar grounds.

FIG. 6

A. α -Picoline (0.1967M/l)/ZrCl₄ (0.0108 g.).

B. Dimethylaniline (0.2277M/l)/ZrCl₄ (0.0308 g.).

Antimony pentachloride acts as a strong monobasic acid in benzoyl chloride and furnishes a monosolvate (Seel, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1943, 252, 24; Paul Bains and Singh, *loc.cit.*) with this solvent, which is dissociated and is soluble in excess of benzoyl chloride. Its dissociation may be represented as :

The initial conductance of the acid solution arises from the dissociation of this solvate, but when a solution of quinoline in benzoyl chloride is added dropwise (Fig. 7), the conductance of the solution increases, which means that a more ionogenic compound is formed.

As the addition of quinoline solution is continued, the conductance rises progressively until it reaches a limiting value corresponding to the formation of a 1:1 complex, benzoylquinolinium hexachloroantimonate, and then falls off beyond this point. No further break in the curve is observed. The yellowish brown solution of antimony pentachloride becomes colorless at the point of maximum conductance and no precipitate appears throughout the titration.

Dimethylaniline (Fig. 7) and α -picoline (Fig. 8), when titrated against antimony pentachloride, provide similar curves. In these cases also, only one break is observed and can be ascribed to the formation of benzoyldimethylanilinium hexachloroantimonate and benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachloroantimonate respectively. No solid separates during the titration.

FIG. 7

A. Dimethylaniline (0.2571M/l)/SbCl₅ (0.0411 g.).
B. Quinoline (0.2384 " / " / 0.0383 g.).

FIG. 8

α -Picoline (0.3176M/l) against SbCl₅ (0.0681 g.).

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzoyl chloride and the acids and bases were purified as already described (Paul, Bains and Singh, *loc cit.*; Paul, Chander and Singh, *loc. cit.*). For the present work benzoyl chloride, purified as above, was again distilled in a special fractionating column and collected at a take-off ratio of 1:5.

For measurements of the specific conductance of the solutions of different bases in benzoyl chloride, special conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.64, kept at a constant temperature of 28°, was used.

The solutions were prepared in a dry box and the transfer of the solutions was carried out with the help of dry nitrogen under pressure. For conductometric titrations a glass conductivity cell, equipped with a microburette, replaceable platinum electrodes and calcium chloride guard tube, was employed. The resistance of the solutions was measured at 28° by using a precision measuring bridge type WBR No. 108 with logarithmic indicator amplifier type, TAV. IKC, No. 034 (Wissenschaftlich-Technische Werkstätten, Wielheim/Oby., Germany).

In Figs. 1-8, molar ratio of acid to base or base to acid has been plotted against relative conductance which is equal to $1/R$. Cell constant has not been taken into account due to the difficulty of placing the electrodes in exactly the same positions in the cell.

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